
Deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.26

Workpackage 6

Responsible partners: BfR, SVA

Contributing partners: APHA, IZSLER,
AGES/Vetmeduni, VRI, WBVR/UU

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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Start Date	01/01/2018 (BIOPIGEE 01/01/2020)
Duration	60 Months (BIOPIGEE 30 Months, requested extension for 6 additional months)

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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Author	Marie Sjölund (SVA), Tamino Dubbert / Elke Burow (BfR)
Other contributors	Task participants from: SVA, EMU, BfR, WBVR/UU, VRI, IZSLER, APHA, AGES/Vetmeduni
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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s): via Zenodo

BIOPIGEE

Workshop 3 completed

Participating institutes (in the workshop organisation)

BfR, SVA

Further contributing institutes

IZSLER, APHA, AGES/Vetmeduni, UU, VRI

Background and objective

The workshop was originally planned to take place as a one-day event in conjunction to a relevant conference in order to disseminate results from the BIOPIGEE project, to receive feedback and discuss implementation. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the implementation of the event was delayed and changed to an online format, also split into two different workshops, on primary production and on slaughterhouse biosecurity practice. For the workshop on primary production, stakeholders of the pig industry, agricultural associations, advisory service associations, public health authorities, regulatory authorities, research & academia, veterinarians and those interested in effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to control *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus (HEV) in primary pig production were invited to participate. The objective of the online workshop was to share and discuss results on identified effective biosecurity measures from the BIOPIGEE project and the possible implementations of these measures in practice.

BIOPIGEE project

The zoonotic pathogens *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus can cause acute and chronic diseases in humans. The most common transmission route is assumed to be foodborne from pigs. The aim of the project BIOPIGEE “biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe” of the One Health European Joint Programme is to identify effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures for the reduction of these pathogens in the pig production chain which can be offered for implementation in order to prevent human infections. To achieve this, different literature reviews, field studies, experiments and transmission/cost modelling are carried out. Finally, it is the aim to inform stakeholders like farmers, veterinarians, authorities, and the pig industry about the findings on best biosecurity practice e.g. in the context of workshops.

Invitation and advertisement

Main contact partners at BIOPIGEE partner institutes were informed about and invited to the upcoming primary production workshop via email on 1st July 2022 (see email invitation below). They were further asked to forward an attached invitation (see below) and a preliminary programme from the same date on forward to individuals, groups and institutions in countries in- and outside EU (see

invitation below). Multiple reminders were sent. In parallel the workshop was promoted via a newsletter in OHEJP and repeatedly on Twitter with the help of the OHEJP Communication Team, using a Save the date and a full flyer (see below). Through the information sent, people were provided with a link to an event web page hosted by BfR where they could register for the workshop. A link to the web tool (Webex, BfR) together with the final programme was sent to the registered participants seven days and one day in advance, and on the same day of the workshop.

Invitation (email content)

Dear BIOPIGEE institutional contact partner.

We are pleased to invite you to a **workshop** entitled “**Biosecurity practice in European pig farms**”, organised by the BIOPIGEE project (‘Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe’).

The workshop aims to engage stakeholders in pig production, veterinary services, animal health and biosecurity advice services, and other organisations, interested in biosecurity measures and their effectiveness against Salmonella and hepatitis E virus (HEV) on European pig farms.

We will present outcomes from the BIOPIGEE project on effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures and look forward to discussing these with the workshop participants on how best practice can be implemented at farm-level.

The workshop will take place on 14th September 2022 from 1 to 5 p.m. CET, and will be accessible online. The web link will be sent out to registered participants.

We kindly ask you to forward the attached invitation to the following stakeholders in your country:

- Animal health services
- Biosecurity consulting services
- Veterinary societies
- Pig industry
- Veterinary practitioners
- Key researchers
- Farmers/farming associations
- Agricultural training centres
- Large integrated pig production companies

Many thanks already for spreading the word about the event and thereby helping to create a forum for exciting discussions.

Please keep record of those invited.

Should you have any questions, please don't hesitate to contact biopiqee-coord@bfr.bund.de (Elke Burow) or marie.sjölund@sva.se (Marie Sjölund).

On behalf of the BIOPIGEE consortium,

Marie Sjölund & Elke Burow

This project is part of the One Health European Joint Programme and has received funding from the participating institutes and the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Invitation (attached PDF to email)

**WORKSHOP INVITATION
- results from the BIOPIGEE project**

Salmonella and the hepatitis E virus (HEV) are two important zoonotic infections which can lead to both subclinical infections (infections without symptoms) and production losses in pigs. In addition, they can cause more severe and potentially fatal infections in both humans and pigs. Farmers, veterinarians, and other professionals with pig contacts could be at increased risk of *Salmonella* and HEV infection due to their frequent and intensive contact with pigs. A European consortium known as the BIOPIGEE project ('Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe'; <https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-biopigee/>) has since 2020 conducted research to identify the most effective biosecurity practices that limit the occurrence of *Salmonella* and HEV in pig farms across Europe.

This has been achieved by combining expert solicitations with field work where data on biosecurity practices has been collected and assessed in relation to the presence of *Salmonella* and HEV by collecting faecal samples from pigs on a range of different farm types in the participating countries. In addition, a comprehensive literature review and meta-analysis on effective measures to control both pathogens was carried out. Moreover, the effectiveness of common disinfectants against *Salmonella* and HEV has been studied in experimental laboratory studies. This information has then been used in mathematical models to identify which biosecurity measures are most effective against one, or both, of the pathogens at the lowest cost.

As a final step, we wish to **exchange ideas on effective and cost-efficient measures and how to implement best practice in an online workshop**. We are therefore pleased to invite you to participate in the final online workshop on Wednesday 14 September 13:00 to 17:00 CET.

To register for the event, please follow this link:

https://www.bfr-akademie.de/english_int/biopigee-2022.html

On behalf of the BIOPIGEE consortium,

Marie Sjölund & Elke Burow

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OHEJP BIOPIGEE T6.3, Workshop-Invitation, 30.06.2022

Save the Date flyer (Twitter)

IMAGEWIKIMEDIA

Save the Date!
One Health EJP
OHEJP BIOPIGEE Project Workshop:
Biosecurity measures in primary pig production
to control *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus

Date: 1-5pm CEST, 14th September, 2022

Location: Online

Audience: Veterinarian, farming and agriculture associations, advisory service associations, public health authorities, regulatory authorities, those interested in effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to control *Salmonella* and hepatitis E in primary pig production

Registration: [here](#)

@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPBIOPIGEE #StrongerTogether

Full flyer (Twitter)

One Health EJP
OHEJP BIOPIGEE Project Workshop:
Biosecurity measures in primary pig production
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Registration: [here](#)

@OneHealthEJP ONE Health EJP
#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPBIOPIGEE #StrongerTogether

Salmonella and the hepatitis E virus (HEV) are two important zoonotic infections which can lead to both subclinical infections (infections without symptoms) and production losses in pigs.

In addition, they can cause more severe and potentially fatal infections in both humans and pigs. Farmers, veterinarians, and other professionals with pig contacts could be at increased risk of *Salmonella* and HEV infection due to their frequent and intensive contact with pigs.

The One Health EJP European consortium **BIOPIGEE** project (Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe) has, since 2020, conducted research to identify the most effective biosecurity practices that limit the occurrence of *Salmonella* and HEV in pig farms across Europe.

This has been achieved by combining expert solicitations with field work where data on biosecurity practices has been collected and assessed in relation to the presence of *Salmonella* and HEV by collecting faecal samples from pigs on a range of different farm types in the participating countries.

In addition, a comprehensive literature review and meta-analysis on effective measures to control both pathogens was carried out. Moreover, the effectiveness of common disinfectants against *Salmonella* and HEV has been studied in experimental laboratory studies. This information has then been used in mathematical models to identify which biosecurity measures are most effective against one, or both, of the pathogens at the lowest cost.

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Registration: [here](#)

IMAGE: WIKIMEDIA

@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPBIOPIGEE #StrongerTogether

Workshop programme

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Workshop Programme One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Date / Time	14 th September 2022 / 13:00 – 16:50 CET
Venue	Online Workshop
Meeting	OHEJP BIOPIGEE Workshop 3 'Biosecurity practices for European pig farming'
Room	Hosted by BfR online

13:00-16:50 BIOPIGEE Online Workshop 14th September 2022

Biosecurity Measures to Control *Salmonella* and Hepatitis E Virus (HEV) in European Primary Pig Production

Chair: BfR/Elke Burow - Chat: BfR/Tamino Dubbert - Notes: SVA/Marie Sjölund

1. Session - Theoretical introduction

13:00-13:10	Welcome from BfR/ Department Biological Safety and Introduction to this OHEJP Event (BfR/Dr. Niels Bandick)
13:10-13:30	Introduction to the Pathogens <i>Salmonella</i> and HEV (VRI/Ivan Rychlik, UU/Marina Meester)
13:30-13:45	T5.2 Evidence from Literature Review and Meta-analysis (APHA/Elisabeth Waller)
13:45-14:00	T5.4 Expert Opinion results (APHA/Erika Galipó)
14:00-14:10	Questions & Discussion
14:10-14:30	<i>Short break</i>

Chair: UU/Tijs Tobias - Chat: SVA/Marie Sjölund - Notes: IZSLER/Enrico Pavoni

2. Session – Field studies of the effectiveness of biosecurity on HEV and *Salmonella* presence

14:30-14:50	T2.2 Application of the Biosecurity Protocol: Results and Discussion (APHA/Hannah Jones, BfR/Tamino Dubbert)
14:50-15:10	T2.4 Field Studies related to HEV transmission and effect of Cleaning & Disinfection: Results and Discussion (UU/Marina Meester)
15:10-15:20	Questions & Discussion

Programme of BIOPIGEE Online Workshop 14th September 2022 hosted by BfR online Page 1/2

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

15:20-15:35 Short break

Chair: APHA/Robin Simons - Chat: VetMedUni/Nikolaus Huber - Notes: APHA/Elisabeth Waller

3. Session – Studies on the Cost-Efficiency of selected Biosecurity Measures

15:35-15:55 **T4.4 Cost-Effectiveness of Specific Biosecurity Measures to Reduce Salmonella/HEV Along the Pork Production Chain** (VetMedUni/Clara Bester)

15:55-16:05 **Questions & Discussion**

16:05-16:10 Short break

Chair: APHA/Richard Smith - Chat: VetMedUni/Nikolaus Huber - Notes: APHA/Elisabeth Waller

4. Session – Discussion

16:10-16:40 **Feedback, what can be done/how to use findings and motivate farmers to implement biosecurity measures**
(Introductory slides, BfR/Elke Burow)

16:40-16.50 **Closing of the Workshop** (APHA/Richard Smith; BfR/Elke Burow)

OHEJP BIOPIGEE partner institutes:

Participants

In total 153 people including 26 BIOPIGEE members registered for the workshop (Table 1) and 109 participants attended the workshop. The professional background of the participants was mainly pig production, veterinarians and pig practitioners. Also consultants, officials and scientific backgrounds were represented. Participants came from mainly from European countries, but also from India, South America (Brazil), USA and Canada, Africa, Scandinavia, and the Middle East.

Table 1: Registered people and there indication on location and professional background

Countries	Pig production / pig practitioners / veterinarians	Academia & research	Government agencies / public health / animal health / food safety	Others	Total
Austria	1	1	1	3	6
Belgium	1	0	0	0	1
Bulgaria	0	0	0	1	1
Brazil	0	1	0	0	1
Canada	1	0	0	0	1
Cyprus	2	0	0	0	2
Germany	7	4	2	4	17
Denmark	0	0	0	1	1
Estonia	3	1	3	3	10
Spain	0	1	1	0	2
France	1	2	0	2	5
Great Britain	21	6	10	12	49
Ireland	2	0	0	0	2
India	0	1	0	0	1
Indonesia	0	1	0	0	1
Italy	4	1	3	8	16
Jordan	0	0	1	0	1
Kenia	0	1	0	0	1
Nigeria	1	2	1	1	5
The Netherlands	3	4	3	0	10
Norway	2	0	0	0	2
Nepal	1	0	0	0	1
Poland	1	0	0	0	1
Portugal	0	0	1	1	2
Romania	0	0	1	0	1
Sweden	3	0	2	4	9
Ukraine	0	2	0	0	2
United States	0	1	1	0	2
Total	54	27	30	40	153

Conduction of the workshop

The workshop went according to plan. During the first session two speakers introduced the participants to the background of the two pathogens *Salmonella* and HEV. Following, the evidence collected from the literature review and meta-analysis and the results from the expert opinion study were presented. In the second session, the results from the application of the biosecurity questionnaire and the field studies related to HEV transmission and effect of cleaning & disinfection were presented. Topic of the third session was the cost-effectiveness of specific biosecurity measures to reduce *Salmonella*/HEV along the pork production chain. In the final session, the discussion topic was how to use the findings and how to motivate farmers.

Discussion points, questions, feedback (anonymous)

- What is seroprevalence of HEV in humans?
 - It is hard to give you one number because of different assays and populations tested in each country, but often seroprevalences of 10 to 20 % are reported.
- On topic that “not sharing equipment” was a risk factor
 - Could it be that these farms do not pay attention to their equipment as they are not sharing it (but using for several runs); and others (sharing it) are aware of the risk and really disinfect it before using it?
 - In one of the papers (the UK study), the authors did mention that they could not state what kind of equipment had been shared or whether it had much (if any contact) with the pigs. In the Reunion Island, they were specifically looking at exchanging breeding equipment, although the authors provided no further comment on their findings from this in their article.
 - In the UK study, sharing equipment was most identified in farms selected that did not know their *Salmonella* status prior to the study; so it may be that the farms who share their equipment have measures in place as they are aware of the risk, but not of their status.
 - It definitely should be taken as a proxy though rather than as a direct Biosecurity measure!
- Is there a minimum threshold for the presence of those organisms? I mean, should 1% or 5% makes a difference? Are You can answer that in the chat. Thank you.
 - I think the risk modellers have looked into the impact upon of different thresholds on the number of potential human cases. I wonder if anyone on the workshop has any info on this
 - I don't believe there is a minimum threshold at which you could conclude there would be no human cases, but a lower prevalence will generally result in fewer human cases, albeit that relationship is not necessarily linear
- What is the main function for carcass storage in a farm? Does it for storing slaughtered pigs? If so, then the farms sampled are acting as slaughter houses as well?
 - The carcass storage is for pigs which die on farm, rather than those going for slaughter
- Do you know how long (an average time) one carcass stays at the farm, waiting for the pick up or incineration?

- I honestly don't know what is typical and we haven't measured this info. Maybe there are also differences between countries. I would maybe refer again to @Hannah if she has an idea on that?
- I would not know the average time to collection, I would expect it to vary between countries and also regions within countries. In the UK I would think it ranges from a few hours up to a week in a locked, leak-proof container, but we do not have any data on this. Some farms will have incinerators so perhaps only a matter of hours.
- I agree with you - we should discuss these issues in a broad way. Especially if you think about One Health.
- Were they open water tanks? Maybe if pressure washing there could have been aerosols created which contaminated the water during cleaning
 - They were open drinkers, so it is possible your thesis is right
 - Broiler production systems gave up with water header tanks within rooms, even when fitted with lids. *Salmonella*, *E.coli* and campylobacter logged. Now all bulk water tanks external to broiler rooms
- Birds as vectors, 7.5% of bird faecal samples on 6 commercial pig units sign positive for *S. typhimurium* and *S.reading*. Also *brachyspira* @3%
- I was wondering, whether you could share how/where testing for HEV RNA was performed for your study. If in more than one laboratory, were tests were harmonized over the laboratories, was there a harmonized cut-off used?
- That's really interesting, thank you! We have certainly seen *Salmonella* in bird faeces before, so it's interesting we are also seeing HEV RNA present in bird faeces, too.
- Will be interesting to know the location of where the bird faeces were sampled from. As mentioned, there is a possibility that it is contamination and that the HEV RNA was not in the bird faeces. There was a relatively high copy number in some dust samples.
- Bird faeces collected from aseptic mesh screens erected above pig feeders six hours before collection and tpt [?] to labs and also from live captured birds. But environmental contaminations always possible, yes!
- When did anal plugging take place in pigs?
- Are you considering any additional benefits/impacts to the cases and costs you studied?
 - We would like to, but this depends on data availability.
 - Yes, but specifically what about the impacts on productivity?
 - Yes, it is considered already for *Salmonella* as it has been studied, but there is no data on this for HEV – this is likely because HEV is mostly asymptomatic in humans so not much data is generated. We will also look at the impact of [...].
- Is it including hospital and community cases in this analysis?
 - Yes – severity of cases is listed up to and including death for *Salmonella*. For HEV, severity was also looked at, but measured slightly differently – e.g. only considers HEV Genotype 3 cases.
- Apologies for leaving. Thank you and very interesting.
- Can biosecurity measures be the same for viral and bacterial pathogens? At least disinfection will be different for non-enveloped viruses. Can we learn from Food preparation location (like Codex WO/FAO) ; how to inform food handlers
- Just to contribute to the discussion. We need to monitor these risk factors for quite a long time, to be able to measure most of the proposed measurements. We found 5 mutations in

water before reaching pig farms - and 22 in water after the farms. How that will end up in our cities?

- [...]from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*
- We use this guidance in slaughter houses (industry guidance): chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://bmapa-my.sharepoint.com/personal/info_britishmeatindustry_org/Documents/BMPA-WebsiteFiles/PublicWebsiteFiles/Our%20work/BMPA%20Pork%20Scheme/Scheme%20Modules/Lorry_Washing_Guidance.pdf?ga=1
- I cannot unmute myself but I totally agree with [...] that we should publish much more in magazines for farmers!
- I'm having tech issues but that could be something that AHDB could help with - signposting some of the practical messaging etc.
- Great project! Thanks for an interesting afternoon!
- Thank you and some very interesting topics for improvement that are focused and science based.
- Thanks very much - great event
- Thank you - very interesting.
- Thank you for your interesting presentation.

Conclusion

The workshop was successful in informing about the BIOPIGEE project, presenting and discussing (oral and chat) the results of the studies and investigations, and advancing the topics of implementation of biosecurity measures, engagement of farmers and stakeholders and the need to share results in a broader community. The online format had many benefits over the original plan of having the event in presence and connected to a conference. Among others, the workshop sessions were open to a larger audience and interested participants of various professions and countries could participate.

Future work

Publications on effective biosecurity measures and other results of the BIOPIGEE project, are in the process and will be published in the near future. All results in OHEJP will be published 'open access' and by that be accessible without any fee barriers for all stakeholders and other interested people.

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